

A Critical Study on Using English Movies in English Classrooms at Tertiary Level in Bangladesh

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***Abstract:** Keeping the tech-savvy learners of 21st century in mind, classroom teaching is no longer confined to only printed texts. To reach the entertainment lover learners, it has become a trend of the time to ensure edutainment where education is disseminated to the learners through entertainment. This paper attempts to investigate how far it is effective to use English movies in enhancing students' linguistic competency along with textual comprehension at tertiary level 'English classrooms' through a questionnaire survey and a semi-structured interview. Participants, both teachers and learners, of this study are from the department of English of four private universities of Bangladesh. Though, in general, 'English classrooms' refer to only English language classrooms, in this paper the term 'English classrooms' includes both English language and English literature classrooms. The paper critically seeks to explore the perceptions of both teachers and students on issues like: (i) To what extent teachers and students are aware of the effectiveness of using English movies in 'English classrooms? (ii) Is there any gap between the synchronization of the objectives, process and outcomes of the approach?, and (iii) How to optimize the effectiveness of using English movies in 'English classrooms' facing the probable challenges?*

***Keywords:** Tech-savvy, trend of the time, Edutainment, English classrooms, optimizing effectiveness of English movies*

1. Introduction

When the medium of instruction in the undergraduate programs of tertiary level of education, is a language other than the learners' mother tongue, it is quite bewildering for the learners to comprehend the subject matter if they do not have sufficient proficiency in that target language. Even after having English language as a subject for twelve years, learners at the tertiary level

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of Bangladesh (except the ones of English medium) are eventually found not to have up- to- the mark proficiency to grasp and present the subject matters of their undergraduate programs. The reasons behind this deficiency are multifaceted and varied including dull and unstimulating teaching learning materials, memorization based assessment system, lack of natural exposure

to the target language and so on. Moreover, absence of edutainment in the language teaching materials has made the task of language acquisition ever tiresome and frustrating.

Edutainment refers to the entertainments specifically designed to be educational and in this age of innovation, many language practitioners and scholars are inclined to find out different ways of edutainment as emotional pleasure has a direct connection to comprehension and learning of a language. Integration of movies into course curriculum is one of the most popular formats of edutainment. Researchers are trying to scrutinize to what extent movie activities can be appropriately diversified to complement the present teaching learning process of English. Because of the substantial effects of movies on the enhancement of learners' basic language skills: listening, reading, speaking and writing, many language practitioners ascertained the integration of movies to the existing curriculum as Kabooha (2016) referred to the studies of Baratta& Jones (2008), Martin &Jaén (2009),Ismaili (2013), Rokni&Ataee (2014),and Yaseen&Shakir, (2015).

Nevertheless, movies received attention as a powerful teaching learning material in EFL classrooms being a gateway of providing opportunities for learners to experience the natural communications of the native speakers in authentic settings (Herron, et al., 1992;SwaffarVlatten, 1997; Seferoğlu, 2008;). In addition, many language practitioners identified that movies not only offer the possibility of diversified classroom activities but through a display of target language culture, movies also work as a motivating factor for learners to learn the target language (Kusumarasyati, 2004; Luo, 2004; Brown, 2010). Movie adaptations of famous and current novels are equally proved to be entertaining and engaging for the students in the western world specially who are pursuing their higher studies in English literature. However, if we look into the practice of deliberate use of movies in enhancing the linguistic proficiency as well as in boosting up the textual understanding of tertiary level students of department of English in Bangladesh, we notice a

non-defined approach to be prevailing. So far integrating movie activities into present curriculum is concerned, there is no sign of concentration. The teachers of the respective department are found to instruct their students to watch English movies for the improvement of their linguistic competency and the textual understanding of the literary pieces of their syllabus without any further reflection on the effects of such practice let alone the optimization. Therefore, the current research aims to have a critical study on the present status of using English movies in English classrooms (i.e. English literature and language) in four private universities of Bangladesh.

2. Literature Review

The practice of using English movies in nurturing the linguistic competency of learners has been prevalent for years. Since 1970s this practice has been on work when technology started to find its way into English language classrooms. However, the only available technological tool for this approach was then DVD players, difficult for the teachers to use because of its lack of automation and demanding the teachers to bring extra equipment (Yamanaka, 2002, p.48). In the course of time, with the emergence of internet facility, this laborious phase of technology was over. DVD player- based customized video resources for the EFL/ ESL learners were replaced by the movies of real life contexts and of different kinds of native speakers (King, 2002, p.510). In fact, that was the beginning of 'Edutainment' through English movies which was eventually found to have a great impact on the enrichment of learners' linguistic proficiency and textual comprehension.

While some of the English language practitioners concentrated on the movie activities as a medium of exposure to the target language culture (Xing, 2011) and a platform to acquaint learners with the target language vocabulary and idiomatic expressions (Herron and Tomasello, 1992, p.481), some of them aimed for further utilization of the approach. It is shown that movies can be applied to teach target language grammar (Mushtaq&Zehra, 2016), to develop interactional skills (Keene, 2006), to retain target language vocabulary (Brown, 2010), to increase critical thinking skills (Eken, 2003), and to improve intellectual capacity (Swaffar&Vlatten, 1997) of the students.

There are also several studies that emphasize the role of movies in helping out students with all the four language skills. In fact, it is demonstrated in the

study of Herron and Hanley (1992) that the background information, which acts as the very raw material in stimulating all the four language skills, can be provided by screening movies. In another study of Hanley and Herron (1995) it is evident that by providing interesting and motivating clues, movie watching can also help in developing writing skills. Besides, Ismaili (2013) cited the research of Pezdek, Lehrer, and Simon (1984) to illustrate the role of movie fragments in recalling information of reading and listening. Ismaili (2013) also mentioned numerous studies on the use of videos especially to develop listening comprehension (Wetzel, Radtke & Stern, 1994; Ginther, 2002; Gruba, 2006; Suvorov, 2008). In addition, the research conducted by Rimi (2016) pointed out the effectiveness of using movies in developing the pronunciation and speaking skills of the tertiary level students of Bangladesh which was matched with the studies of Seferoglu (2008), Florence (2009), and Mirvan (2013).

Researchers were also found to pinpoint the value of using subtitles over not using them (King, 2002; Massi & Blazquez, 2008; Hayati & Mohmadi, 2011; Rokni and Ataee, 2014 as cited in Kabooha, (2016). Besides viewing of the movies in full length versus viewing them in segments was also a matter of concern for some studies (King, 2002 as cited in Kabooha, 2016).

However, the effectiveness of using movies in developing students' linguistic efficiency and textual comprehension can only be materialized if proper procedure with specific educational objectives can be employed. The teacher requires to ensure interactive viewing of the given movies as most of the time, according to Keene (2006), movie activities are assigned as home activities and thus are considered by the students as a way of escapism, relaxation and entertainment (p.223). Movies with pure entertainment has a risk of producing passive viewers. So, movies should be chosen with the view of confirming 'edutainment' where education would be the main goal and entertainment would be the motivating medium to reach that goal. To meet this end, Stephens, Ascencio, Burgos, Diaz, Montenegro, and Valenzuela (2012) suggested to consider the richness of content whereas King (2002) stressed on the assurance of less complex and non-offensive movies in compliance with the target students.

As far as the procedure of movie activities is concerned, Keene (2006) found the pre-viewing activities with the students about the movies and the

characters to be effective in sustaining the interest of the students to watch the movie till the end. Besides, Li (2012) found that a five minute introduction to the movie followed by a brainstorming session between the teacher and the students regarding the theme, new vocabulary and expressions to be very effective in the comprehension of the movie to be assigned.

Although many studies are conducted on different issues regarding the effectiveness of using movies in English language classrooms, a very few studies are found to concentrate on the use of movies for accelerating reading comprehension (except Weyers, 1999; Mirvan, 2013 & Ismaili, 2013) while usage of movies in enhancing textual comprehension along with linguistic development is almost rare. The present study concentrates on exploring the perceptions of Bangladeshi teachers and Bangladeshi students of department of English on the effectiveness of using English movies in 'English classrooms'. In doing so, the study critically problematizes the rate of satisfaction of the teachers and of the students on the effectiveness of using English movies in 'English classrooms'.

The research questions are:

- (i) To what extent are teachers and students aware of the effectiveness of using English movies in 'English classrooms'?
- (ii) Is there any gap between the synchronization of the objectives, processes and outcomes of the approach? , and
- (iii) How to optimize the effectiveness of using English movies in 'English Classrooms' facing the probable challenges?

3. Methodology

The current study adopted a mixed-method approach consisting of both quantitative and qualitative data, and then develops analyses relying on the integrated strengths of both data to present a detailed understanding of the research problem (Creswell, 2015). Two types of data collection techniques were implemented: i) Questionnaire Survey and ii) Semi-structured informal interview. The Questionnaire survey was carried out with both teachers and learners whereas for the purpose of interview only the teachers were approached. The teachers' questionnaire consisted of 8 questions and the students' questionnaire consisted of 7 questions. Most of the questions of these questionnaires were kept open ended with a purpose of eliciting the

participant's careful opinion. The total sample of participants consisted of 40 teachers and 60 learners. The teachers teach both English language and English literature courses to the students of department of English. The levels of proficiency of the learners are: pre-intermediate and intermediate. Most of the participants (85% teachers, and 100% students) belonged to a focused group in a sense of experiencing English movies in their classrooms. Demographics of the participants were classified as 67.5% female teachers, 32.5% male teachers, 50% female learners and 50% male learners and teachers between the ages of 23 to 71 years and learners between the ages of 20 to 24 years. For the informal interview, only the interested and willing teachers were chosen. They were 8 in number which is 5% of the total teacher participants representing the four universities under the current research. The whole process of survey was conducted in the physical presence of the researchers so that necessary intervention could be extended in case of complementing the proper understanding of the participants. Google form was replaced with the face to face interview to accelerate the involvement of the participants with the research. However, the researchers employed a convenience sampling method to select the participants because of the limitation of time, money and workforce. As far as the selection of the institutions was concerned, institutions practicing innovative techniques in acceleration of quality education and willing to share respective experiences were preferred.

4. Findings and Discussion

4.1 The Teachers' and Students' Questionnaires

The review of the findings of the study is given on the basis of the research questions as follows:

(i) To what extent are teachers and students aware of the effectiveness of using English movies in 'English class rooms'?

A descriptive statistical analysis of the responses given by the teachers and the students demonstrated that on a general level, both of them considered the integration of movies into English classrooms as effective as 85% (34)

teachers of the present study were affirmative about the effectiveness of using movies in their classrooms while for the students, it is 100%(60).

Only 6 (15%) teachers answered in negative in the question of using movies in English classrooms. Two of them did not even feel the necessity of using English movies in their classroom. One justified not using movies in his classroom because of the risk of exposing his students to a sub-standard variety of a language and for another, it is time consuming with a less effective impact on teaching grammar to his students. Mentionable observation regarding these opinions is that none of these teachers had ever used English movies in their classrooms and without any experiments they had just made such assumptions. The opinions of the rest of the teachers with a negative answer can be summarized as unsuitability of the nature of the course, dependence on short video clips and lack of trust on movies as original representation of the text.

In naming the most frequently used movies (top 5) in their classrooms, 40 teachers listed more than 90 movies in total. The most common ones are closely connected with literary texts which they usually teach like *Pride and Prejudice*, *Great Expectations*, *A Passage to India*, *Tess of the d'Urbervilles*, *Gulliver's Travels*, *The Old Man and the Sea*, *Macbeth*, *The Merchant of Venice*, *Arms and the Man*, *As You Like It*, *Julius Caesar*, *Robinson Crusoe*, *Twelfth Night*, *Animal Farm* etc. The second best common ones beside these were: *Gladiator*, *Troy*, *Forrest Gump*, *Wuthering Heights*, *A Beautiful Mind*, *My Fair Lady*, *The Pursuit of Happiness*, *Harry Potter*, *The Shawshank Redemption*, *Brave Heart* and *Roman Holiday*, which represents the Bangladeshi teachers' fascination for orienting their students to the world famous classics.

(ii) Is there any gap/laps between the synchronization of the objectives, process and outcomes of the approach?

The purposes with which the teachers (34 in total) used movies for English classrooms are found to be varied:

SL	Purposes of using English movies in English classrooms	Total response (in number)	Total response (in percentage)
1.	Complementing textual understanding	18	53%
2.	Arresting attention through visuals	10	29.41%
3.	Ensuring edutainment	9	26.47%
4.	Exposing to target language vocabulary and idioms	6	17.64%
5.	Exposing to target language culture and minimizing cultural gap	4	11.76%
6.	Improving critical thinking and analytical skills	3	8.82%
7.	Viewing comprehension	2	5.88%
8.	Building confidence for role playing	3	8.82%
9.	Involving in interactive movie review	2	5.88%
10.	Developing listening skills	8	23.52%
11.	Developing writing skills	2	5.88%
12.	Developing reading skills	2	5.88%
13.	Practicing everyday conversation	3	8.82%
14.	Improving pronunciation and intonation	2	5.88%
16.	Developing as a compassionate human being	1	3%

Table 1: Purposes of using movies in English classrooms from teachers' point of view

As far as benefits of watching movies assigned by the teachers is concerned, the students were given freedom to choose more than one from five benefits set by the researcher. It is noticeable that among 60 students, 54 (90%) agreed to the statement that movies help them in better understanding of the text, 46 (77%) considered movie activities as beneficial for improvement of their listening skill, 40(67%) perceived movie activities as beneficial for enhancement of their speaking skill, 22 (37%) believed that viewing movies improves their presentation skills while 24 (40%) were found to be encouraged for stage performance (as shown in Figure 1).

Figure 1: Benefits of using movies in English classrooms from students' perspectives

In respect of the procedures to be followed during conducting the movie activities, teachers were found not to follow specific steps always. However, the steps they have mentioned can be collated as follows:

Step1: Asking students to watch a text-based/ concept based movie.

Step2: Checking the students' understanding of the text/ the concept through discussion.

Step3: Asking the students whether they have found any dissimilarity with the text, taking quiz, asking them to write a movie review/ asking them to do assignment or poster presentation or stage performance.

However, while inquired about their observations regarding their teachers' planning and process of implementation of the movie activities, 35% of the students were found not to be able to identify the steps.

The most common steps perceived by the rest 65% of the students are as follows:

Step1: Teacher usually talks about the major themes, main characters and setting of the text.

Step2: Teacher encourages the students to watch the major characters, their relationships and the setting of the movie very carefully relating to the text.

Step3: Teacher discusses with the students to find out their understanding and then assign different tasks like writing movie review, doing assignment/ presentation/ performance.

Although the steps mentioned by both teachers and students are eventually found to be matched, there is no mention of any specific pre-viewing, while-viewing and post-viewing activities which is a prerequisite to ensure students' active learning of certain educational objectives.

When students' feedback in customizing teaching approach through English movies is taken into account, 30 (75%) teachers acknowledged taking feedback from their students, 8 (20%) teachers said, "No", while 2 (5%) of them did not answer. Nevertheless, the most common feedback of the students to the respective teachers can be summarized as their ability to recognize the connection between the text and the movie through enjoyment.

(iii) How to optimize the effectiveness of using English movies in 'English classrooms' facing the probable challenges?

Majority of the teachers and the students are found to have a positive response towards the kinesthetic appeal of the selected movies. By putting the students within the target language culture, integration of movies into the English classrooms, has not only helped the students in enhancing their linguistic and interactional proficiency, critical thinking skills, textual understanding including involvement with the respective characters, plot, tone and setting of the texts but also created in them a lifelong fascination for the target language style, motivation for further reading, and personal attachment towards the concepts which remains permanent and continues to stay as a source of motivator to venture such experience in future. However, none of the stakeholders (both teachers and students) are found to be fully satisfied with the rate of improvement and have pointed out some of the challenges on their way to address movie related activities which is illustrated through the following charts:

Figure 2: Challenges of using movies in English classrooms from teachers' perspectives

Figure 3: Challenges of using movies in English classrooms from students' perspectives

Nevertheless, some of the students of 'Literature, Film and Media' course, have pointed out some challenges like nervousness and lack of active group members and props during performance, difficulty in writing scripts and making films, managing camera and other equipment for belonging to a middle economic social class.

In proposing probable solutions, majority of the teachers are found to suggest students watching movies at home to save time of the class while a

good number of students have demanded their teachers' presence during movie screening to be ensured of complete understanding. To manage time constraint, some of the teachers have opined to screen movies in segments with the presence of the teachers while some students suggested to select movies of shorter length. To understand the pragmatic features of the target language culture, teachers have advocated avoiding subtitles whereas majority of the students are found to require subtitles to understand the speech of the characters. Moreover, teachers have emphasized on taking extra caution in choosing movies adjusting with the respective learners' level of age, linguistic capacity and area of interest. Some of the teachers have even suggested to consult experts' opinion in this regard. A few of the teachers as well as a significant number of students have suggested to share movie reviews, detailed discussion of the full text and pre-task brainstorming activity as effective strategies for motivating students to watch text-based movies.

4.2 The Teachers' Interviews

Eight teachers, representing the four universities under this study, were interviewed to complement the findings of the questionnaires. The interviews with the teachers displayed different kinds of reflections. Some of the highlights of their comments are as follows:

T1: "A movie adaptation can never be a substitute of a text. It can only be used as a supporting material to create a lengthy impact of the text in the mind of the students".

T2: "I teach Literature, Film and Media course and show cinemas of different countries to introduce my students with different traditions of world cinema as part of my course requirements."

T3: "I do always prefer to accompany my students during movie activities. To manage time, sometimes we watch the movie in two segments and sometimes we focus only on the crucial scenes. I take a pause before thematically important dialogues and discuss with the students before playing again. I ask them to do role play later but I do not follow a well-organized approach in a sense that I have never given any worksheet to my students during screening time".

T4: "Some of the students are reluctant to take movie activities seriously.

They remain so relaxed that the teacher's motif of 'edutainment' turns to mere 'entertainment'".

T5: "I assign different movies to different groups of students and ask them to find out the most important scenes chronologically. Then they have to rewrite the dialogues of those scenes and remake a shorter version of the movie. I count the scripts as their assignments and the performance as their presentation. To save time, I do not burden them with costume designing".

T6: "I use movie clips a lot to clarify thematic concepts of every course I teach. To do so, I need to do a lot of homework".

T7: "I have found my students instrumentally motivated. For grade, they work on the assigned activities. They want to show off to their friends of other universities that they are working on a movie to improve their linguistic proficiency. However, due to lack of follow-up on my part, they cease to do movie based activities after the end of the course. Here 'entertainment' is preferable by the students to the 'edutainment'".

T8: "While screening movies and documentaries, I create a different atmosphere other than the regular classes. My students respond enthusiastically. At the end of the course, my students have to perform on stage with proper props".

When taken together, the findings of the questionnaires and the interviews of the teachers illustrate that in department of English of Bangladeshi private universities, movies are usually used for complementing the understanding of the literary texts under respective syllabus. Both teachers and students are found to be highly positive about the effectiveness of using English movies in English classrooms. However, most of the participants are found to perceive a possibility of optimizing the approach.

Although teachers of the courses based on developing different linguistic skills try to use movie activities as a way of motivating students to learn the target language, neither the teachers of Literature nor the teachers of Linguistics courses is found to practice a systematic approach. Movies are actually used to arrest students' attention through visuals. There is a significant absence of well-organized pre-viewing, while-viewing and post-viewing

movieactivities. Although both teachers and students have agreed to a common procedure of using movies in English classrooms, no worksheet is provided for the students with focused educational

objectives-neither linguistic nor thematic. In this respect, the research of Ismaili(2013) in the context of South East Europe can be taken into account where the researcher exposed the experimental group of students with organized pre-viewing, while-viewing and post-viewing movie activities and thus eventually found the experimental group outsmarting the controlled group not only in thematic understanding but also in improvement of vocabulary, writing skill and speaking skill.This implies that organized methodology is indispensable to keep students focused and perform better on the given tasks.

Along with better textual understanding, the students of the current study are also found to be benefitted in enhancing their listening and speaking skills by using movies in English classrooms. However, none of the instructors are found to maintain a reflective journal, which by reminding the teacher of the best practices and the most avoidable, could be a much effective way in optimizing the effectiveness of using English movies in English classrooms.

Most of the time, insufficient administrative and infrastructural support and time constraint with a burden of syllabus completion, pose impediments in carrying out movie-based activities. To cope up with these situational obstacles, many teachers ask the students to watch the given movies at home without any well-organized worksheets which plausibly results in pure ‘entertainment’ instead of ‘edutainment’. In some of the cases, students are even found to prepare their assignments by copying from google without watching the actual movie.

5. Recommendations

- *Subtitle*

It is found that on the issue of availing subtitle, the position of the learners and the teachers is just the opposite. While for the former, subtitle is a healing tool in comprehending the rapid speed of the characters, for the later, subtitle is a hurdle on the way of properly visualizing the movie

including the characters' pronunciation, intonation, facial expressions and the episodic significance of the whole movie and thereby the text. The argument is, while reading the subtitle, a learner might not be able to simultaneously follow and be attentive to the issues mentioned above and therefore, the ultimate purpose of watching a movie might substantially be lost. Teachers can resolve this contradiction by motivating students to watch movies without subtitles from the very beginning of the movie-based activities.

- *Pre-watching, While-watching and Post-watching activities*

The learners can be largely engaged in activities through giving some simple tasks which of course, include pre-watching, while-watching, and post-watching activities. While-watching activities are especially essential to address those students who consider the whole endeavor casually. As a part of the pre-watching activities, learners can be asked to know a little bit about the subject, plot, and characters of the movie. The course instructor can play a vital role regarding this. She/he may brief the learners about the movie before playing it. It is also useful to give the learners some simple questions to explore while watching the movie. If the learners are not given any work sheets with instruction during while-watching phase, they can be simply asked to point out some interesting and/or ambiguous issues like unknown vocabularies, character's / characters' role and the like. Some researchers may question the activity of finding out new vocabularies as a barrier to entertainment. In this regard, the issue of edutainment should be prioritized to the issue of mere entertainment. Moreover, while watching a movie, the instructor may pause at important/vital points and make the floor open for all to discuss different aspects of the episode/s or scene/s. Even lack of fluency can be accepted to encourage the less confident students. Thus, a classroom can be interactive and engaging, which will ultimately make the class lively, interesting, enjoyable and educative.

- *Time Constraint*

Time constraint is one of the key issues that most of the participants are concerned with. Many have mentioned that video clips should be preferred to the whole movie in the classroom to cope up with the class time. However, the researcher's observation against watching video clips of the movie is that it might have a risk of not providing the comprehensive

knowledge of the movie and thereby the text. So, the full version of the movie is suggested to be played in segments with the presence of the respective teacher.

- *Edited Versions*

Some participants opine that edited version of the movie should be played in the classroom to comply with Bangladeshi culture as they claim to avoid obscene ones. In this regard, the researcher argues on the careful selection of the movie. However, if the text demands such scenes which are addressed as so-called 'obscene', it cannot be avoided. Moreover, what is obscene in Bangladeshi culture may be the very right scene in respective culture around which the text is written and the movie is made. The researcher also believes that it is the teachers' responsibility to make their learners matured and ready to deal with all kind of situations and accept what is preferable to individual culture and custom, and reject what is not.

- *Institutional training of teachers*

Institutional training is necessary for further optimization of the approach.

- *Reflective Journals*

Teaching focus should be explicit. Writing reflective journals can help in this regard.

6. Pedagogical Implications and Scope for Further Research

- (i) The study can provide a list of movies to be considered by the scholars and curriculum designers who recommend inclusion of movies into English studies.
- (ii) It can contribute to the process of quality enhancement while teaching through movies.
- (iii) It can make teachers of English literature to rethink of their role in improving students' linguistic competence along with thematic knowledge.
- (iv) It also has a clear message to convey to the ELT (English Language Teaching) practitioners who are wondering about editing/ shortening movies as well as of allowing students to watch movies with subtitles at home.

- (v) Based on this study further research can be conducted on designing worksheets for pre-watching, while-watching and post-watching tasks on selected movies to be screened in English classrooms.

7. Limitations

Although the study was conducted across different proficiency levels, the absence of specific strategies and specific educational objectives on the part of the instructors resulted in casual participations for many of the students while they answered the questionnaires.

In this study, only four private universities in the capital were addressed. One limitation was the inability to explore a good number of private and public universities inside and outside the capital city Dhaka. Moreover, a number of private universities with high ranking of IQAC (Institutional Quality Assurance Cell) could not be explored because of their rigid research policy. It is assumed that they are not willing to share their teaching learning strategies with researchers of other institutes. The possibility of losing business on their part could also not be figured out.

8. Conclusion

The present study reflects the fascination for movie-based learning of two important stakeholders namely students and teachers of department of English in Bangladeshi private universities. The participants are found to perceive a very positive attitude towards using English movies in English classrooms with a view of enhancing conceptual understanding of the literary texts of their syllabus as well as knowledge of vocabulary, pronunciation and communication skills. This perception also complies with the National Education Policy of Bangladesh (2010) where educators are advocated to prepare their students with real life language skills so that they can know about the target language culture and values, pursue higher education and attempt to create access to local and global employment (National Curriculum, 2012, p.2). However, even with a positive attitude, the students under the current study are eventually found not to be fully satisfied as far as their linguistic proficiency is concerned and thus to perceive a possibility of better optimization of the mentioned movie-based teaching learning approach. To fulfill this demand, teachers require to be careful in choosing movies with specific pedagogical purpose in mind. Meaningful pre-watching,

while-watching and post-watching tasks should be designed for English classrooms to ensure edutainment instead of mere entertainment and thus to extract the maximum benefit of this excellent teaching learning approach.

References

- Baratta, A., & Jones, S. (2008). Using film to introduce and develop academic writing skills. among UK undergraduate students. *Journal of Educational Enquiry*, 8(2), 15-37.
- Brown, S. K. (2010). Popular films in the EFL classroom: Study of *methodology*. *Procedia–Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 3, 45-54. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2010.07.011>
- Creswell, J. (2015). *A concise introduction to mixed methods research*. London, England: SAGE
- Eken, A.N. (2003). “You’ve got mail”: A film workshop. *ELT Journal*, 57(1), 51-59. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/elt/57.1.51>
- Florence, Y. (2009). *Learning English through films : A case study of a Hong Kong class*. University of Hong Kong.
- Ginther. (2002) Context and content visuals and performance on listening comprehension stimuli. *Language testing*, 19 (2), 113-167.
- Gruba, P. (2006) Playing the videotext: A media literacy perspective on video-mediated L2 listening. *Language learning and technology*, 10 (2),77-92.
- Hayati, A., & Mohmedi, F. (2011). The effect of films with and without subtitles on listening comprehension of EFL learners. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 42(1), 181-192. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8535.2009.01004.x>
- Hanley, J., & Herron, C., A. (1992). Using video to introduce children to a foreign culture. *Foreign Language Annals*, 25,419-426. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1944-9720.1992.tb01122.x>
- Ismaili, M. (2013). The effectiveness of using movies in the EFL classroom: A study conducted at South East European University. *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, 2(4), 121-132. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5901/ajis.2012.v2n4p121>
- Kabooha, R. H. (2016). Using Movies in EFL Classrooms: A Study Conducted at the English Language Institute (ELI), King Abdul-Aziz University. *English Language Teaching*, 9(3), 248-257.

doi:10.5539/elt.v9n3p248

- Keene, M. D. (2006). Viewing video and DVD in the EFL classroom. *Bunkyo Gakuin University Journal*, 8(1), 217-234.
- King, J. (2002). Using DVD feature films in the EFL classroom. *Computer Assisted Language Learning*, 15(5), 509-523. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1076/call.15.5.509.13468>
- Kusumarasyati. (2004). Listening, viewing and imagination: Movies in EFL classes. 2nd International Conference on Imagination and Education Vancouver, Canada, July 14-17, 2004.
- Li, C. (2012). Are they listening better? Supporting EFL college students' DVD video comprehension with advance organizers in a multimedia English course. *Journal of College Teaching & Learning*, 9(4).
- Luo, J. J. (2004). Using DVD films to enhance college freshmen's English listening comprehension and motivation. Unpublished Master thesis, National Tsing Hua University, Hsinchu. Taiwan, R.O.C.
- Martín, M., & Jaén, M. (2009). Teaching conversation through films: A comparison of conversational features and collocations in the BNC and a micro-corpus of movies. *The International Journal of Learning*, 16(7), 445-458.
- Massi, M., & Blázquez, B. (2008). Exploiting DVDs' extra features: An added bonus in the EFL class. *Humanising Language Teaching*, 10(4).
- Mirvan, X. (2013). The advantages of using films to enhance student's reading skills in the EFL classroom. *Journal of Education Practice*, 4(13).
- Mushtaq, H. & Zehra, T. (2016). Teaching English Grammar through Animated Movies. *Nust Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 2(1), 77-87.
- National Curriculum and Textbook Board (2012), National Curriculum 2012, English Curriculum For Eleven and Twelve.
- Rimi, R., (2016). Effects of Showing Movies in a Speaking. *International Journal of Current Research*. doi: 8.33716-33722.
- Rokni, S., & Ataee, A. (2014). Movies in EFL classrooms: With or without subtitles. *The Dawn Journal*, 3(1), 715-726.
- Secules, T., Herron, T. & Tomasello, M. (1992). The Effects of Video Context on Foreign Language Learning. *The Modern Language Journal*, 76 (4), 480-490.
- Seferoğlu, G. (2008). Using feature films in language classes. *Education Studies*, 34 (1), 1-9.
- Swaffer, J. & Vlatten, A. (1997). A Sequential Model for Video Viewing in the Foreign Language Curriculum. *The Modern Language Journal*, 81 (2), 175-188.
- Stephens, C., Ascencio, R., Burgos, A., Diaz, T., Montenegro, J., & Valenzu

- ela, C. (2012). Film circles: Scaffolding speaking for EFL students. *English Teaching Forum*, 2, 14-20.
- Suvorov, R. (2008). Context visuals in L2 listening text. The effectiveness of photographs and videos vs. audio-only format. Master thesis, Iowa State University, Iowa
- Weyers, J. R. (1999). The effect of authentic video on communicative competence. *Modern Language Journal*, 83(3), 339-349.
- Wetzel, Radtke & Stern, (1994). Instructional effectiveness of video media. Using DVD Films to Enhance College Freshmen's English Listening Comprehension and Motivation, MA thesis, National Tsing Hua University, Taiwan.
- Xing, C. (2011) How to Use English Movies to Improve a Student's Listening and Speaking Ability in Chinese ESL Culture Learning Classrooms. University of Wisconsin, Platteville.
- Yaseen, B., & Shakir, H. (2015). Movies effects on EFL learners at Iraqi school in Kuala Lumpur. *International Journal of Education and Literacy Studies*, 3(3), 31-36. <http://dx.doi.org/10.7575/aiac.ijels.v.3n.3p.31>
- Yamanaka, M. (2002). *The Use of Movies in EFL Tuition*. Gifu City, Japan: Gifu Women's University.

Appendices

1. The Questionnaire for Teachers:

A Critical Study on Using English Movies in English Classrooms

The study intends to find out the extent of using English movies in English classrooms to substantiate the teaching learning process in the field of both language and literature. Based on the reflections of the participants, the paper will be prepared for publication. Please respond and justify your answers as accurately as possible.

Teacher's Name

(Optional): _____

Gender: # Male # Female

Age: _____

Affiliation: _____

Teaching Experience: _____ Years

Area of teaching: # English literature # English language # Applied linguistics and ELT

1. A. Do you consider using English movies effective in your classrooms?

Yes # No

1. B. If "No", please write your opinion on the ground _____

2. Mention the age level of the students you teach: _____ Years

3. Name the top 5 movies you frequently recommend to your students: _____

4. A) What are the purposes of using English movies in your class?
4. B) How do you achieve those purposes?

Step 1:

Step

2:_____

Step

3:_____

5. A. Do you take feedback from your students to customize your teaching approach through English movies? # Yes # No

5. B. Mention the most common feedback from your students:_____

6. A. Is there any special outcomes of using English movies on your students? # Yes # No

6. B. If yes, what are those?

6. C. Are you satisfied with your students' achievements/ performance? # Yes # No # Somewhat

6. D. What else can you do for further improvement?

7. A. What are the challenges you face while using English Movies?

7. B. What can be the possible solutions?

8. Give your overall observation on using English Movies in your classes including your suggestions:_____

2. The Questionnaire for Students:

A Critical Study on Using English Movies in English Classrooms

The study intends to find out the extent of using English movies in English classrooms to substantiate the teaching learning process in the field of both language and literature. Based on the reflections of the participants, the paper will be prepared for publication. Please respond and justify your answers as accurately as possible.

Student's Name: _____

Gender: # Male # Female Age: _____

Institute: _____

1. A. Do your teachers use English movies in your classroom? # Yes # No

1. B. Is it effective? # Yes # No

2. A. What benefits do you get after watching English movies (you can choose more than one)?

- Better understanding of the text
- Improvement of listening skill
- Improvement of speaking skill
- Improvement of presentation skill
- Encouragement of stage performance

2. B. To achieve those benefits, do your teachers follow any specific steps? # Yes # No

3. C. If "Yes", what are those?

Step 1: _____

Step 2: _____

Step 3: _____

4. Are you satisfied with your achievements (after completing the movie based activities)?

Yes # No # Somewhat

5. What else can you do for further improvement?

6. A. What are the challenges you face while performing movie-based activities? _____

6. B. What can be the possible solutions?

7. Give your overall observation on using English Movies in your classes including your suggestions:
